

The Effect of Study Techniques on Memory Retention in Different Subjects

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Abstract

Various study techniques are used by students to achieve good grades and remember tough topics easily. Students often struggle to remember things or learn new topics. A majority of students study hours and hours but tend to get zero results. The problem is not with their hard work and dedication but with their wrong study techniques. Studying 2 focused hours with proper techniques is better than studying 4 hours without understanding anything. Study techniques are lifesavers for students. This research uses experiments with subjects trying various techniques and noting down their outcomes. The result is that not every technique is made for every subject. A method can be effective in social science but not in mathematics. Social studies are theory-heavy, and mathematics is purely numerical, so just repeating the same set of words in your mind wouldn't be effective for mathematics.

The Effect of Study Techniques on Memory Retention in Different Subjects

Study techniques are methods used by learners to understand and recall information. This includes various methods such as: active recall, repetition, Pomodoro technique, Feynman's method, etc. It can reduce stress and completes time consuming tasks quickly.

In the ancient times, learning was primarily oral only because there was lack of study materials and copies, people used oral communication to transfer their knowledge to next generation. Ancient techniques included mnemonics and repetition. The ancient Greeks believed that practicing same set of things daily will create place for new memory in brain and practicing it daily will increase the average storage skills to up to twice its usual capacity. The Greeks named it 'loci', a mnemonic involving learning through visualization.

In Middle Ages, formal education was mostly limited to religious and elites only. Students often copied texts manually which enhanced retention. In 17th-19th century, the reach of education was getting broader and scientific methods determined learning. People observed, experimented and used structured plans and syllabus to study.

In early 20th century, researchers focused on psychology of learning. Psychologists such as Skinner, Watson and Pavlov researched on behaviorism and concluded that reinforcements and practice improve memory. Similarly, Piaget and Vygotsky focused on understanding mental processes like memory, attention and comprehension (i.e., cognitive psychology). Moreover, study techniques like SQ3R and Cornell note taking system were also developed.

Method

Participants

Five students, all males from class 11 at Mithila Institute of Technology participated in this research. The participants ranged in age from 16 to 18 years old ($M = 16.6$, $SD = 0.55$). All participants are currently studying same subjects (PCMB). All the participants had somewhat similar academic performance.

Participants were given same set of rules, instructions and taught exact techniques (when and how to perform them). Participation was voluntary and no monetary support was provided to them. All participant agreed to be on this research and those who were below the age of 18 took the permission of their parents.

Materials

The study material included same books for each participants and varied to five subjects: English, Mathematics, Physics, Biology and Chemistry. All the subjects choose were familiar as they were already studying those in high school.

Four study techniques were used:

1. Active recall
2. Repetition
3. Pomodoro technique
4. Feynman technique

To measure the memory retention, all the participants had to study each subject individually for four-week, one technique per week per subject and at the end of every week a test was taken.

To measure effectiveness, four chapters from each subject was taken, each having equal

weightage. The chapters were changed for every topic. It took sum total of 20 weeks to complete this experiment. The participants learned 20 chapters from different subjects. The grades of test were considered the effectiveness of each techniques.

Apparatus

Following equipment were used in this experiment:

1. A stopwatch (to ensure every participant studies for equal time and to track test duration).
2. Computer (to record grades and prepare spreadsheet and to keep track of their progress).

Procedure

Participants were informed about the purpose and methods of this study and consent was taken. All participants were given clear instructions on study procedures, and were trained properly on how to correctly apply those techniques.

The study was conducted in the duration of 20 weeks. All participants studied five subjects (English, Physics, Chemistry, Mathematics, Biology), one study technique was applied per week for each subject. All participants were able to use all four techniques in all five subjects. The instructions were well structured to ensure each technique was used properly, thereby controlling for subject difficulty as a potential confounding variable.

For each week, participants were given one chapter per subject and instructed to strictly use the only materials provided to them. All chapters were selected to have similar weightage in order to control content variation. Participants studied under similar conditions under the supervision of their parents.

At the end of every week, participants completed test based on the subjects they studied. The test duration was kept same for each participants. The final scores obtained were recorded and used as measure of effectiveness of different study techniques across different subjects. After the completion of the experiment, the participants were briefed about the outcome of this experiment.

The active recall technique involves remembering topics and then self-testing without notes.

The repetition technique involves repeating the same things over and over again until you remember it. The Feynman technique involves imagining yourself as teacher and teaching the stuffs you learnt. Finally, the Pomodoro technique involves learning for a fixed time (For example: 25 minutes) then resting for some time (For example: 5 minutes).

Results

The research found out that the brain needs some time to process contents that have been feed. Overloading brain with all the stress and learning things for whole day does not help much until you are studying smartly.

A table of result for 5 participants was prepared and an average table (Table 1) was made.

Subject	Active Recall	Repetition	Pomodoro	Feynman
English	8.6	6.8	8.4	7.4
Mathematics	2	3.8	6.8	7.2
Physics	4.2	3.2	6.4	6.8
Biology	6.2	6	6.8	6.2
Chemistry	6	4.8	6.8	7

Table 1. (Average of all the data collected)

The data shows us that active recall worked best for English while Pomodoro technique worked best for Biology, Feynman technique worked best for 3 subjects; Mathematics, Physics and Chemistry. This result gives us insight about how does these techniques work.

The active recall worked best for English because you need to keep the structure, format and grammar in mind and it's not that hard you can easily remember it while it does not require

stressing your brain with too much unwanted information, so active recall worked best here.

Mathematics is the subject of logic and reasoning. It requires practice to master it. Active recall and repetition turned out to be worst methods to study math as you cannot practice numerical problems there and remembering formula while not practicing questions won't build up strong memory. It can surely build short-term memory. The Feynman technique worked best for mathematics as you need some time to process information.

Physics and Chemistry are theory, numerical and concept heavy subjects and we often mistake here by overloading our brain. Teaching others can be helpful as it is not our daily job and our brain remember it easily; visualization adds another advantage here. The Feynman's method worked best here. While Biology is theory-heavy, it requires frequent rest, so Pomodoro technique worked best here.

We can notice different pattern in *Table 1*;

1. Pomodoro is best overall technique. The average of score of all five subject is highest in Pomodoro.
2. Feynman technique is very close to Pomodoro overall. It is best for those subject which needs understanding, explanation and problem solving,
3. Repetition is the weakest among all.
4. Active recall is also not much affective as a single technique but using it simultaneously with other techniques can be good.

Discussion

The hypothesis that study techniques improve your grade is real. However, it was surprising that active recall performed bad, if you go to any online sources, you will find active recall on top but my opinion is that integrating active recall with other techniques can be helpful. My finding aligns with other research suggesting Pomodoro and Feynman's techniques as best for studying. However, my study provided broader and subject-wise measure of effectiveness of those techniques. The broader behavior of this study suggests that studying is not only about choosing right technique but also about how humans learn and how do the brain process those information. Our study concluded that not every technique is made for every subject. This means that brain processes different type of information differently. Our brain retains information efficiently when thinking, explaining and solving is involved rather than passively reading. Deep understanding of any subject leads to better memory retention. My results are valid but it may differ from other researches as this research was concluded in small-level.

This research raises some big questions that whether the effectiveness of study techniques depend upon nature of subject or individual cognitive abilities. The research was done with only five students, so a large study involving more participants may give different results. The tests were done every weekend so we cannot conclude that the memory will last how long. A further question is that just using a single technique is more effective or combining different techniques for better results. One major gap in this study is that this study primarily focuses on short-term academic performance rather than applications. Moreover, the study does not define the role of dedication, interest, motivation, confidence, interest and mental fatigue, which influence learning.

The findings of this study contribute to study of how memory and learning function in different subjects. This research concludes that a short and focused study hour is more effective than unfocused study hour, it does not depend how much time you spend on studying but how much time you are focused and concentrated while studying. This supports existing theories that supports active learning. Human mind works better when it is challenged not simply feed information.

This study is important because it addresses common problems faced by almost every student who study for hours without sleeping and skipping lunches. This study highlights need of focus and concentration. This study concludes that understanding-based, reasoning-based and challenging study is far better than passive learning.

References

Pavlov, Watson, Skinner, and behaviorism. (2020, October 23). *Social Sci LibreTexts*. [https://socialsci.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Psychology/Introductory_Psychology/General_Psychology_for_Honors_Students_\(Votaw\)/01:_History_of_Psychology/1.06:_Pavlov_Watson_Skinne_r_And_Behaviorism](https://socialsci.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Psychology/Introductory_Psychology/General_Psychology_for_Honors_Students_(Votaw)/01:_History_of_Psychology/1.06:_Pavlov_Watson_Skinne_r_And_Behaviorism)

Davis, M. (2022, June 20). *Method of loci: Ancient mnemonic technique used by Greeks and Romans effectively double brain's memory storage skills*. *Science Times*. <https://www.sciencetimes.com/articles/38274/20220619/ancient-mnemonic-technique-double-brains-memory-storage-skills-study-reveals.htm>

Mellentine, J. (2023, November 21). *Piaget vs. Vygotsky: Theory, similarities & differences*. *Study.com*. <https://study.com/learn/lesson/piaget-vs-vygotsky-theories-differences-purpose.html>